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Optical Determination of the State of Charge in a Vanadium Redox Flow Battery

Ana González-Espinosa¹, Antonio Lozano¹, José Barranco¹, Manuel Montiel^{1,2}, Félix Barreras¹

¹ Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CSIC), C/Miguel Luesma Castán, 4, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain

² Fundación Agencia Aragonesa para la Investigación y el Desarrollo (ARAID), Av. de Ranillas I-D, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain

e-mail presenting author: ana.gonzalez@csic.es

Determination of the State of Charge (SoC) is essential for the proper operation and control of a Redox Flow Battery. In the specific case of all-vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB), the electrolytes are solutions of vanadium salts ($V^{2+}/V^{3+} // VO_2^+/VO^{2+}$) in acidic medium. As the charge depends on the concentration of each vanadium species, the SoC can theoretically be defined as

$$\text{SoC} = \frac{V^{2+}}{V^{2+} + V^{3+}} = \frac{VO_2^+}{VO_2^+ + VO^{2+}}$$

This expression assumes that the system is balanced, but this hypothesis is not verified in practical systems. Crossover of vanadium ions from a half-cell to the other through the membrane, oxidation of the V^{2+} ions and gas side reactions, especially the hydrogen evolution reaction at the negative electrode during charging, always lead to an imbalance between the negative and positive electrolytes.

In most cases, SoC is derived from the measurement of the open circuit voltage (OCV). It can be inferred from the voltage of the operating battery, but this is very inaccurate. To improve the measurement, an auxiliary cell hydraulically connected in parallel and in open circuit can be used, independently measuring the voltage of each half-cell. Still, for imbalanced systems, the method is not precise. Alternative ways to determine the SoC have been devised, measuring the variation of voltage with time, the electrolyte viscosity and conductivity, or the speed of sound in each solution. This work examines the use of absorption spectroscopy to calculate the SoC. Each one of the vanadium species has a well-defined absorption spectrum in the visible region. Measuring the absorbed light at specific wavelengths and applying the Beer-Lambert law, the concentration of the different vanadium ions, V(II), V(III), V(IV) and V(V), can, in theory, be determined. This method has been successfully tested for low vanadium concentrations (see [1] for concentrations up to 0.3 M). However, for the real concentrations used in VRFBs (>1.5 M) solving the problem is not straightforward. VO_2^+ and VO^{2+} react to form an intermediate species $V_2O_3^{3+}$ whose concentration and absorption spectrum is *a priori* unknown [2], and it is difficult to be sure that the Beer-Lambert equation is satisfied. Furthermore, the absorption spectra might depend on the charging voltage. An experimental calibration is proposed.

Figure 1: Left: Electrolyte droplet samples at different SOC. Right: Absorbance of V(IV)/V(V) mixtures for different V(IV) 4 percentages. Concentration 1.65 M. Charging voltage 1.8 V.

References

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